

Synthesis of some new 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-(3-chloro-4-substituted aryl-2-oxo-azetidine)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles : Antifungal and antibacterial agents

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Abstract : 1,2,3-Benzotriazole on treatment with ethyl chloroacetate gave ethyl 1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-acetate **1** which on amination with hydrazine hydrate afforded 1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-acetic acid hydrazide **2**. The compound **2** on cyclisation with CS₂-KOH yielded 2-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazole **3**. The compound **3** on further treatment with hydrazine hydrate gave 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole **4**. The compound **4** on condensation with various carbonyl compounds furnished 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-arylidene-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles **5**. β-Lactam moiety was introduced in the compound **5** through cycloaddition using chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of (C₂H₅)₃N to yield 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-(3-chloro-4-substituted aryl-2-oxo-azetidine)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles **6**. The structures of all the products were characterized by microanalytical data and spectroscopy techniques. All the synthesized products were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Trichoderma viride*.

Keywords : Substituted triazoles, biological activity.

In the past years, the literature is enriched with progressive findings about the synthesis and pharmacological action of fused heterocycles. 1,2,3-Benzotriazole nucleus is associated with diverse biological and pharmacological activities¹. In the light of these observations we report herein the incorporation of 2-oxo-azetidinone moiety in 1,2,3-benzotriazole which was used as the target for chemical modification through 1,3,4-triazole nucleus in one frame work (Scheme 1) and to assess their biological activity.

Synthetic procedure :

1,2,3-Benzotriazole on treatment with ethyl chloroacetate afforded ethyl 1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-acetate **1** which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate resulted in the formation of 1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-acetic acid hydrazide **2**. The compound **2** on cyclisation with CS₂-KOH (alco) yielded 2-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazole **3** which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate resulted in the formation of 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole **4**. The compound **4** on condensation with various selected carbonyl compounds furnished 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-arylidene-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole **5**. The compound **5** on reaction with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of (C₂H₅)₃N furnished 3-(1,2,3-benzotriazolyl-

methyl)-4-(3-chloro-4-substituted aryl-2-oxo-azetidine)-5-mercapto-1,2,3-triazoles **6**.

Antimicrobial activity : The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. nigar*, *A. flavus*, *F. oxysporium* and *T. viride* by filter paper disc technique² at two concentrations (100 and 500 ppm) and antibacterial activity of against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* at two concentration (50 and 100 ppm). Standard antifungal griseofulvin and antibacterial streptomycin were also screened under the similar conditions for comparison. Results are presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrometer (ν_{max} in cm⁻¹, KBr) and ¹H NMR spectra on Bruker DRX-300 in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by silica gel 'G' coated TLC plates. The mass spectrum was recorded on Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer.

Ethyl 1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-acetate 1 : Ethyl chloroacetate (0.06 mol) was added to a solution of 1,2,3-benzotriazole (0.06 mol) in methanol (40 mL) and the reaction mixture was

Scheme 1

refluxed for about 3 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* to get a solid product which was purified over the column of silica gel and eluted with chloroform. The eluate was concentrated and the residue was crystallized from CHCl_3 to give **1**, yield 85%, m.p. 130–132 °C (Found : C, 58.49; H, 5.33; N, 20.43. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 58.53; H, 5.36; N, 20.48%); IR : 3254, 3078, 2960, 2800, 1363, 1000, 1596, 1470, 942, 870, 740 (1,2,3-benzotriazole), 2830, 1481, 1206 (N-CH_2), 1710 ($>\text{C=O}$), 2898, 2875, 1435, 698 (CH_2 and CH_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$: 3.60 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2$), 7.26–7.96 (4H, m, Ar-H), 1.18 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.10 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

1,2,3-Benzotriazole-1-acetic acid hydrazide 2 : A mixture of compound **1** (0.03 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.03 mol) in methanol (50 mL) was refluxed on a water bath for about 6

h. It was cooled, filtered and concentrated to get a solid compound which was passed through a column of silica gel and eluted with chloroform. The eluate was concentrated and crystallized from chloroform to give compound **2**, yield 76%, m.p. 76–77 °C (Found : C, 50.23; H, 4.69; N, 36.61. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5\text{O}$ requires : C, 50.26; H, 4.71; N, 36.64%); IR : 3250, 3075, 2957, 2796, 1359, 996, 1594, 1465, 940, 868, 735 (1,2,3-benzotriazole), 3375, 3326 (NHNH_2), 1675 (amido carbonyl), 2828, 1477, 1210 ($>\text{N-CH}_2$); $^1\text{H NMR}$: 3.67 (2H, s, N-CH_2), 4.50 (2H, s, NH_2), 8.12 (1H, s, CONH), 7.28–7.99 (4H, m, Ar-H).

Table 1. Antifungal data

Compd.	<i>A. nigar</i>		<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>F. oxysporium</i>		<i>T. viride</i>	
	100 ppm	500 ppm	100 ppm	500 ppm	100 ppm	500 ppm	100 ppm	500 ppm
5a	+	++	+	+	++	+++	++	++
5b	++	+++	++	+++	++	+++	++	+++
5e	++	+++	++	++	++	+++	+++	++++
5h	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++
5k	-	-	+	++	+	+	++	++
5n	+	+	-	-	++	++	++	+++
6a	++	++	+	++	-	-	++	++
6b	+	++	++	++	+	++	++	+++
6c	+++	+++	++	++	++	+++	++	+++
6h	++	++	+	++	++	+++	++	+++
6k	++	++	+	+	+	++	++	++
6n	++	++	+	++	+	++	++	++
GF	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

GF = Griseofulvin; inhibition diameter in mm; (-) 5 mm; (+) 5–10 mm; (++) 10–16 mm; (+++) 16–24 mm and (++++) 24–32 mm.

2-(1,2,3-Benzotriazolylmethyl)-5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazole 3 : A mixture of compound **2** (0.027 mol) in ethanol (30 mL) and CS_2 (0.027 mol) (ethanolic KOH, 0.1 N, 15 mL) was refluxed on a water bath for about 6 h. It was cooled, filtered and concentrated to get a product which was purified over the column of silica gel using benzene as an eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was crystallized with chloroform to give compound **3**, yield 69%, m.p. 84–85 °C (Found : C, 46.32; H, 2.29; N, 30.00. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}_5\text{OS}$ requires : C, 46.35; H, 3.00; N, 30.04%); IR : 3247, 3072, 2955, 2794, 1355, 994, 1592, 1463, 938, 865, 732 (1,2,3-benzotriazole),

Note

Chart 1

2025, 1464, 1208 ($>\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), 1610 ($>\text{C}=\text{N}-$), 1029, 1268 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$), 2589 ($-\text{SH}$); $^1\text{H NMR}$: 3.69 (2H, s, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), 4.12 (1H, s, SH), 7.24–7.94 (4H, m, Ar-H).

3-(1,2,3-Benzotriazolymethyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole 4 : A mixture of compound 3 (0.015 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol) in methanol (40 mL) was refluxed on a water bath for about 12 h, cooled and concentrated to get a solid product which was purified over the column of silica gel using chloroform as an eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was crystallized from chloroform to furnish 4, yielded 82.0%, m.p. 62–63 °C (Found :

C, 43.70; H, 3.61; N, 39.64. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{N}_7\text{S}$ requires : C, 43.72; H, 3.64; N, 39.67%; IR : 3243, 3070, 2952, 2790, 1352, 990, 1598, 1460, 932, 863, 729 (1,2,3-benzotriazole), 2823, 1460, 1212 ($\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), 1609 ($>\text{C}=\text{N}$), 2585 ($-\text{SH}$), 3370, 3320 ($-\text{NH}_2$); $^1\text{H NMR}$: 3.65 (2H, s, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$), 4.18 (1H, s, SH), 4.46 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.21–7.91 (4H, m, Ar-H).

3-(1,2,3-Benzotriazolymethyl)-4-arylidene-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole 5a : A mixture of compound 4 (0.004 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.004 mol) in methanol (30 mL) was refluxed on a water-bath for about 3 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to yield a product which was passed over

the column to silica gel using chloroform as an eluant. The eluate was concentrated and the product was crystallized from chloroform to give compound, yield 69%, m.p. 56–58 °C (Found : C, 57.28; H, 3.84; N, 29.20. $C_{16}H_{13}N_7S$ requires : C, 57.31; H, 3.88; N, 29.25%); IR : 3240, 3066, 2950, 2786, 1348, 987, 1595, 1456, 928, 860, 722 (1,2,3-benzotriazole), 2827, 1464, 1206 (N-CH₂), 1600 (>C=N), 2582 (-SH); ¹H NMR : 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.14 (1H, s, SH), 4.45 (1H, s, N=CH), 7.18–7.89 (9H, m, Ar-H).

Table 2. Antibacterial data

Compd.	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	
	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm
5a	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	++
5b	++	+++	+	+	++	++	++	+++
5c	++	+++	++	++	++	+++	++	++
5h	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
5k	++	+++	++	++	++	+++	++	++
5n	++	++	+	++	+	+	+	+
6a	++	++	+	+	-	-	+	++
6h	+	++	++	++	++	+++	++	+++
6e	++	++	++	+++	++	++	++	+++
6h	++	+++	++	+++	++	+++	++	++
6k	++	++	++	+++	++	+++	+	+
6n	+	+	+	+	+	++	-	-
SM	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

SM = Streptomycin; inhibition diameter in mm; (-) 7 mm; (+) 7–15 mm; (++) 15–23 mm; (+++) 23–28 mm; (++++) 28–35 mm.

Other compounds **5b-p** were synthesized similarly using different carbonyls. **5b** (Ar = 2-ClC₆H₄), yield 73%, m.p. 71–72 °C; **5c** (Ar = 3-ClC₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 79–80 °C; **5d** (Ar = 4-ClC₆H₄), yield 70%, m.p. 75–76 °C; **5e** (Ar = 2-BrC₆H₄), yield 69%, m.p. 79–80 °C; **5f** (Ar = 3-BrC₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 84–85 °C; **5g** (Ar = 4-BrC₆H₄), yield 70%, m.p. 80–81 °C; **5h** (Ar = 2-NO₂C₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 60–62 °C; **5i** (Ar = 3-NO₂C₆H₄), yield 69%, m.p. 63–64 °C; **5j** (Ar = 4-NO₂C₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 68–69 °C; **5k** (Ar = 2-MeOC₆H₄), yield 65%, m.p. 61–62 °C; **5l** (Ar = 3-MeOC₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 60–61 °C; **5m** (Ar = 4-MeOC₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 60–61 °C; **5n** (Ar = 2-MeC₆H₄), yield 63%, m.p. 68–69

°C; **5o** (Ar = 3-MeC₆H₄), yield 64%, m.p. 69–70 °C; **5p** (Ar = 4-MeC₆H₄), yield 66%, m.p. 68–69 °C.

3-(1,2,3-Benzotriazolylmethyl)-4-(3-chloro-4-substituted aryl-2-oxo-azetidine)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole 6a : A mixture of compound **5a** (0.002 mol) in methanol (30 mL) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.002 mol) using Et₃N (0.002 mol) was stirred for about 40 min followed by reflux on a water bath for about 2 h. It was cooled, filtered and concentrated to get a solid compound which was passed through a column of silica gel and eluted with chloroform. The eluate was concentrated and the product was crystallized from chloroform to give compound **6a**, yield 64%, m.p. 58–59 °C (Found : C, 52.44; H, 3.35; N, 23.78. $C_{18}H_{14}N_7OSCl$ requires : C, 52.49; H, 3.40; N, 23.81%); IR : 3237, 3064, 2948, 2783, 1345, 983, 1590, 1453, 925, 857, 720 (1,2,3-benzotriazole), 2824, 1462, 1203 (>N-CH₂), 1601 (>C=N), 2578 (SH), 1760 (β-lactam), 760 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR : 3.68 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.10 (1H, s, -SH), 5.19 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, CHCl), 4.19 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, NCH), 7.14–7.85 (9H, m, Ar-H); MS at *m/z* : 411 (M⁺), 378, 350, 322, 293, 279, 251, 231, 223, 203, 180, 152, 132, 118, 90 (Chart 1).

Other compounds **6b-p** were synthesised similarly using **5b-p**. **6h** (Ar = 2-ClC₆H₄), yield 73%, m.p. 56–57 °C; **6c** (Ar = 3-ClC₆H₄), yield 70%, m.p. 58–59 °C; **6d** (Ar = 4-ClC₆H₄), yield 71%, m.p. 57–58 °C; **6e** (Ar = 2-BrC₆H₄), yield 69%, m.p. 60–61 °C; **6f** (Ar = 3-BrC₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 62–63 °C; **6g** (Ar = 4-BrC₆H₄), yield 67%, m.p. 61–62 °C; **6h** (Ar = 2-NO₂C₆H₄), yield 63%, m.p. 68–70 °C; **6i** (Ar = 3-NO₂C₆H₄), yield 64%, m.p. 70–71 °C; **6j** (Ar = 4-NO₂C₆H₄), yield 64%, m.p. 67–68 °C; **6k** (Ar = 2-MeOC₆H₄), yield 63%, m.p. 65–66 °C; **6l** (Ar = 3-MeOC₆H₄), yield 62%, m.p. 64–65 °C; **6m** (Ar = 4-MeOC₆H₄), yield 61%, m.p. 67–68 °C; **6n** (Ar = 2-MeC₆H₄), yield 68%, m.p. 59–60 °C; **6o** (Ar = 3-MeC₆H₄), yield 66%, m.p. 58–59 °C; **6p** (Ar = 4-MeC₆H₄), yield 67%, m.p. 61–62 °C.

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